

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ALI****FIRST NAME: SARA****PROGRAM CODE : DCCS****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3 %

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE DCCS ACA- 401D

1. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving _____ to the author of that source of information.
 - Name
 - Money.
 - Credit.¹**
 - Website link.

2. Which of the following is correct about source of where the information is taken?
 - Plagiarism is right.
 - It is ethical.
 - It is a serious academic offense that can have serious consequences.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34

- It is fair to take someone's work and not give them credit
3. A period is known as
- A full point.
- A full stop.**³
- Either a full point or a full stop.
- None of the above.
4. At early stages of research finding a question and imaging a tentative answer is found. This tentative answer is called?
- Working title
- Working thesis.
- Working hypothesis.**⁴
- Research design.
5. A _____ is an assertion supported by your whole research argument
- Claim.**⁵
- Hypothesis.
- Abstract.

² Ibid.

³ Ibid., 31.

⁴ Turabian Kate L., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth Edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 58.

⁵ Ibid.

- Title.
6. The two main systems within the Chicago style guidelines are
- Notes and Bibliography.
 - Author and Date.
 - Notes/Bibliography and Author/Date.**⁶
 - Notes/Date and Author/Bibliography.
7. The word CMS stands for
- Chicago manual of style.**⁷
 - Chicago manual for syllabus.
 - Clear manual of style.
 - Chicago manual of systems.
8. The facts of publishing usually includes three elements the place of publication, the publisher's name and
- The month of publication.
 - The year of publication.**⁸
 - The copyrights information.
 - Volume number.

⁶ Ibid., 141.

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Ibid., 181.

9. _____ is the legal right of an owner of created material to control copying and ownership of that material

- Title page.
- Abstract.
- Table of contents.
- Copyright.**⁹

10. The abstract, limited to _____ words, is a concise summary description of the study

- 300.
- 150.
- 350.**¹⁰
- 500.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* Fourth Edition (Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications, 2018), 68.

¹⁰ Ibid., 68.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.